

Metal Carboxylates of Cobalt and Praseodymium in Solid-State and Their Physicochemical Properties

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Abstract

The physicochemical properties of cobalt and praseodymium (Caprate) soaps in their solid forms using infrared (IR) spectroscopy, thermal analysis, and X-ray diffraction provide intricate insights into their molecular organization, thermal characteristics, and crystalline structures. IR analysis reveals the presence of fatty acids in a dimeric state due to hydrogen bonding, contributing to the partial ionic nature observed in the soaps. X-ray diffraction measurements confirm the double-layer structure in both cobalt and praseodymium soaps by calculating long spacings. Thermal analysis demonstrates that the decomposition reaction follows zero-order kinetics, with activation energies of 0.00 kJ/mol in both cobalt and praseodymium (Caprate). Thus, exploring the solid-state physicochemical attributes of these soaps offers valuable insights into their structural, thermal, and crystalline properties.

Keywords: *Metallic Soaps, Fatty acids, thermal analysis, IR spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, Soaps.*

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Introduction

Metallic soaps are water-insoluble metal salts (other than alkali metals) of higher fatty acids. Metal soaps are surface active agents that adsorb at the solids' surface. The coexistence of both lyophilic and lyophobic moieties in a single molecule makes metal soap research crucial in both academia and industry. Many different sectors have found uses for metal soaps, including those dealing with drugs, textiles, rubber, chemicals, plastics, mining, processing of ore, manufacturing of petrochemicals, adhesives, and electroplating. The use of soap, however, is mostly dependent on empirical information, and the choice of soap for a given purpose is influenced by economic considerations. These metal soaps can be synthesized through processes like double decomposition (metathesis), direct reaction of carboxylic acid with metal oxides, hydroxides, and carbonates, or direct reaction of metals with molten fatty acid (Smith, 2019; Arend, et al., 2011; Baij, et al., 2018; Otero, et al., 2014; Hermans, et al., 2015; Meilunas, Bentsen, & Steinberg, 1990; Neonufa, et al., 2018; Margaret, et al., 2016; Dwivedi, Gangwar, & Sharma, 2014; Gupta, et al., 2012; Gabrieli, et al., 2017; Nelson, & Taylor, 2014; Singh, Poonia, & Shukla, 2024; Bhutra, Sharma, & Sharma, 2018).

Figure 1. Structure of Metal Carboxylates

Metallic soaps encompass various colloidal stearates, palmitates, or oleates featuring multiple metals, including neodymium, cadmium, aluminium, calcium, magnesium, copper, iron, and zinc (Pratiwi, et al., 2018; Sharma, Saxena, & Sharma, 2017; Platania, et al., 2020; Pereira, et al., 2012; Liang, & Scott, 2014; Gonzalez, et al., 2020; Mesbah, & Francois, 2017). This study represents a continuation of prior research on cobalt and praseodymium soaps (Figure 1), as documented in earlier reports. The study elucidates the decomposition process's reaction order and activation energy by employing infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, and thermal analysis. These analytical techniques offer valuable insights into the solid-state structural properties of the soaps, advancing our understanding of their behavior and potential applications.

Experimental

We used analytical reagent-grade chemicals for the experiment. Before use, we purified the acids by distillation under reduced pressure. We employed a direct metathesis technique to synthesize the Cobalt and Praseodymium soaps. This involved mixing a slightly excess aqueous metal salt solution with the corresponding sodium soap solution (Caprate) while vigorously stirring within a temperature range of 50-60°C (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Proposed Scheme for the Synthesis of cobalt and Praseodymium Caprate

After precipitation, we filtered the solid residues and washed them with distilled water and acetone to obtain the final product." Following the initial air oven drying, we further purified the product

through a vacuum-assisted drying process to ensure its high purity. For the analysis of the fatty acids and their corresponding metal soaps, we utilized the Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two FTIR Spectrometer. The spectra were obtained using the potassium bromide disc technique, covering the range of 4000 – 400 cm^{-1} . X-ray diffraction patterns were collected using a D8 ADVANCE X-ray diffractometer equipped with an XE-T detector. Iron (Fe) fluorescence was induced by copper (Cu) radiation, which was filtered to 100% with zero intensity loss. Metal filters were intentionally omitted to prevent artifacts in the data. The diffraction angle range spanned from $2\theta = <10$ to >80 (where θ is Bragg's Angle), with readings taken up to 0.001. The wavelength of radiation employed was 1.54 Å. The thermal properties of transition and inner transition metal soaps through TGA were analysed using a Thermogravimetric Analyzer, specifically the Perkin Elmer TGA-4000 (2019 model). The experiment maintained a constant heating rate of 20°C per minute within a static air environment to ensure uniform conditions. This report presents a comprehensive analysis of various analytical methods. Each method offers unique advantages and limitations, which were carefully evaluated in this study. Additionally, we thoroughly examined reference materials and real-world applications to identify inherent constraints within each technique.

Table 1. Physiochemical Data of Cobalt and Praseodymium Carboxylate

S.no	Metal carboxylates	Chemical formula	Colour	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Melting point
1.	Cobalt caprate	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19}\text{COO})_2$	Pale purple	401.4	240 °C
2.	Praseodymium caprate	$\text{Pr}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{19}\text{COO})_3$	Pale green	653	300 °C

This thorough comparison of analytical methodologies offers valuable insights to guide future research and help in making informed decisions. By carefully evaluating each method's advantages and limitations, researchers can better understand which techniques are most suitable for their specific objectives. Additionally, by examining reference materials and real-world applications, potential constraints within each methodology can be identified and addressed, ensuring the reliability and accuracy of experimental results. Ultimately, this comprehensive analysis serves as a roadmap for researchers, enabling them to choose the most appropriate analytical approach for their investigations and contribute meaningfully to scientific progress.

Results and Discussion

The provided infrared spectra data for Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) are in Tables 2, and 3 and illustrated in (Figures 3 and 4). along with their corresponding fatty acids, reveal intriguing insights into the chemical properties of these compounds. Notably, distinct vibrations associated with free acids, such as $\nu \text{C}=\text{O}$ (1680 cm^{-1}), $\nu \text{O-H}$ stretch (2660 cm^{-1}), and $\nu \text{O-H}$ out-of-plane deformation (930 cm^{-1}), are conspicuously absent in the spectra of Cobalt and Praseodymium soaps, indicating complex formation involving the carboxylic regions. In the spectra of fatty acids, absorption maxima around 690 cm^{-1} and 550 cm^{-1} are attributed to the bending and wagging modes of the carboxylic group, suggesting alterations in the carboxylic regions upon complex formation. Specifically, in Cobalt and Praseodymium caprate, two absorption bands near 1550 cm^{-1} , 1558 cm^{-1} , and 1550 cm^{-1} , 1531 cm^{-1} , respectively, correspond to the asymmetric and

symmetric vibrations of the carboxylate ion as identified by *Filopoulou, Vlachou, and Boyatzis* (Filopoulou, Vlachos, & Boyatzis, 2021). The absence of the carboxyl frequency around 1680 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Cobalt and Praseodymium soaps suggests complete resonance within the carboxyl group's two C=O bonds, indicating an ionic nature of the metal-to-oxygen bonding. Distinct absorption bands observed at approximately 454 cm^{-1} in the spectra of both Cobalt and Praseodymium soaps correspond to the Co-O and Pr-O bonds, further confirming the

presence of metal-to-oxygen bonding with ionic characteristics. Additionally, the observation that fatty acids adopt a dimeric structure through hydrogen bonding between molecules further enriches our understanding of the chemistry underlying metal soaps. These findings are significant as they shed light on the fundamental nature of the chemical bonds governing metal soaps and offer insights into their potential applications. Understanding the resonance between metal and oxygen atoms within these compounds is crucial for their development in various fields, highlighting the importance of this study in advancing our knowledge of metal soap chemistry.

Table 2. Cobalt Caprate Infrared Absorption Frequencies (cm^{-1}) and Corresponding Fatty Acids and Their Assignments

S.No	ASSIGNMENTS	CAPRIC ACID	SODIUM CAPRATE	COBALT CAPRATE
1	CH ₃ , C-H asymmetrical stretching	2960 W	2940 W	2957 M
2	CH ₂ , C-H asymmetrical stretching	2920 M	2910 M	2923 S
3	CH ₂ , C-H symmetrical stretching	2855 M	2840 M	2853 M
4	OH, stretching	2660 S	-	-
5	C=O, stretching	1680 S	-	-
6	COO-, C-O asymmetrical stretching	-	1550 S	1558 S
7	C-O, stretch, OH in-plane deformation	1430 M	-	-
8	COO, C-O asymmetrical stretching	-	1455 M	1455 M
9	CH ₂ (adjacent to COOH group) deformation	1410 S	1400 W	1411M
10	CH ₃ , symmetrical deformation	1350 M	1330 M	1385 M
11	Progressive bands (CH ₂ twisting and wagging)	1270-1220 M	1330-1200 W	1385-1240 W
12	CH ₃ rocking	1110 M	1100 M	1114 S
13	OH, out-of-plane deformation	930 S	-	-
14	CH ₂ rocking	720 M	720 M	722 S
15	COOH bending mode	690 M	-	-
16	COOH wagging mode	550 M	-	-
17	Co-O bond	-	-	454 M

Figure 3. Absorption Frequencies of Cobalt Caprate

Table 3. Praseodymium Caprate Infrared Absorption Frequencies (cm⁻¹) and Corresponding Fatty Acids and Their Assignments

S.No	ASSIGNMENTS	CAPRIC ACID	SODIUM CAPRYLATE	PRASEODYMIUM CAPRATE
1	CH ₃ , C-H asymmetrical stretching	2960 W	2940 W	2950 S
2	CH ₂ , C-H asymmetrical stretching	2920 M	2910 M	2923 VS
3	CH ₂ , C-H symmetrical stretching	2855 M	2840 M	2853 S
4	OH, stretching	2660 S	-	-
5	C=O, stretching	1680 S	-	-
6	COO ⁻ , C-O asymmetrical stretching	-	1550 S	1531 S
7	C-O, stretch, OH in-plane deformation	1430 M	-	-
8	COO, C-O asymmetrical stretching	-	1455 M	1464 S
9	CH ₂ (adjacent to COOH group) deformation	1410 S	1400 W	1431 W
10	CH ₃ , symmetrical deformation	1350 M	1330 M	1385 S
11	Progressive bands (CH ₂ twisting and wagging)	1270-1220 M	1330-1200 W	1340-1203 W
12	CH ₃ rocking	1110 M	1100 M	1111 M
13	OH, out-of-plane deformation	930 S	-	-
14	CH ₂ rocking	720 M	720 M	722 M
15	COOH bending mode	690 M	-	-
16	COOH wagging mode	550 M	-	-
17	Pr-O bond	-	-	454 W

Figure 4. Absorption Frequencies of Praseodymium Caprate

The analysis of metal soaps using X-ray diffraction is often challenging due to the difficulty in obtaining sizable crystals for detailed single-crystal scanning. In our investigation, we aimed to understand the structural properties of Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) in the solid state by examining their X-ray diffraction patterns, as presented in Tables 4,5 and illustrated in (Figure 5,6). Upon examination of the diffraction patterns, we observed intense peaks resulting from the diffraction of X-rays by planes of Cobalt and Praseodymium ions. These peaks were discernible within a range of 2° to 80° diffraction angles, indicating the presence of well-defined crystal structures within the samples. To determine the interplanar spacings (d) for a set of crystals, we employed Bragg's equation: $n\lambda = 2d \sin\theta$, where λ represents the radiation wavelength. This equation allowed us to derive valuable information about the arrangement of atoms within the crystal lattice and gain insights into the structural characteristics of Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) metal soaps in the solid state. Despite the challenges associated with obtaining sizable crystals, our analysis of X-ray diffraction patterns provides valuable insights into the crystalline structure of these metal soaps, contributing to a deeper understanding of their properties and behavior in various applications.

Table4. X-Ray Diffraction Analysis of Cobalt Caprate

S.No	2θ	θ	$\sin \theta$	$\lambda/2\sin\theta$	d	n	I/I_{max}
1	12.0000	6.0000	0.1045	7.3693	29.47714	4	0.169231
2	15.1000	7.5500	0.1314	5.8626	29.31319	5	0.123077
3	18.1000	9.0500	0.1573	4.8971	29.38276	6	0.134615
4	21.1500	10.5750	0.1835	4.1973	29.38115	7	0.184615
5	24.2000	12.1000	0.2096	3.6748	29.39816	8	0.407692
6	27.2500	13.6250	0.2356	3.2700	29.42995	9	0.223077

7	30.4500	15.2250	0.2626	2.9332	29.33245	10	0.469231
8	33.4500	16.7250	0.2878	2.6767	29.44383	11	0.346154
9	36.6500	18.3250	0.3144	2.4500	29.40014	12	0.307692
10	39.8000	19.9000	0.3404	2.2631	29.41981	13	0.338462
11	43.0000	21.5000	0.3665	2.1018	29.42473	14	0.5
12	46.2000	23.1000	0.3923	1.9634	29.45044	15	0.342308
13	49.5500	24.7750	0.4191	1.8382	29.41087	16	0.365385
14	52.9000	26.4500	0.4454	1.7294	29.39966	17	0.442308
15	56.3000	28.1500	0.4718	1.6327	29.38945	18	0.392308
16	59.7500	29.8750	0.4981	1.5464	29.3825	19	0.388462
17	63.1000	31.5500	0.5232	1.4722	29.44333	20	0.388462

Figure 5. X-Ray Diffraction Analysis of Cobalt Caprate

Table 5. X-Ray Diffraction Analysis of Praseodymium Caprate

S. No	2θ	θ	Sin θ	$\lambda/2\text{Sin}\theta$	n	d	I/Imax
1	10.9500	5.4750	0.0954	8.0808	3	24.24238	0.2224
2	14.6500	7.3250	0.1275	6.0472	4	24.18873	0.5472
3	18.3000	9.1500	0.1590	4.8485	5	24.24228	0.4075
4	21.9500	10.9750	0.1904	4.0498	6	24.29869	0.5197
5	25.7500	12.8750	0.2228	3.4601	7	24.22083	0.2126
6	29.5000	14.7500	0.2546	3.0283	8	24.22605	0.2382
7	33.2500	16.6250	0.2861	2.6948	9	24.25321	0.2283

8	37.0500	18.5250	0.3177	2.4267	10	24.26677	0.1654
9	40.9000	20.4500	0.3494	2.2067	11	24.27374	0.1909
10	44.8500	22.4250	0.3815	2.0211	12	24.25331	0.2008
11	48.8500	24.4250	0.4135	1.8646	13	24.23932	0.1870
12	52.9500	26.4750	0.4458	1.7294	14	24.21226	0.1339
13	56.9000	28.4500	0.4764	1.6184	15	24.27624	0.1890
14	61.2500	30.6250	0.5094	1.5135	16	24.21592	0.1339
15	65.4500	32.7250	0.5406	1.4262	17	24.24495	0.1161
16	69.8500	34.9250	0.5725	1.3467	18	24.24089	0.1220
17	74.4000	37.2000	0.6046	1.2752	19	24.22928	0.1220
18	79.2000	39.6000	0.6374	1.2096	20	24.19112	0.1161

Figure 6. X-Ray Diffraction Analysis of Praseodymium Caprate

The results indicate good crystallinity for Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) as evidenced by the extension of the diffraction patterns up to the 20th order. Based on the relative intensities of the most intense peak, the average long spacings for Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) were calculated to be approximately 29.24 Å and 29.22 Å, respectively. Notably, there is a difference of 0.02 Å between the two, corresponding to double the length of an additional methylene

(-CH₂-) in the fatty acid radical constituents of the soap molecules. It's worth highlighting that the observed values of the long spacings are smaller than the calculated dimensions of the anions obtained from Pauling's values of atomic radii and bond angles. This suggests that there may be factors influencing the crystal lattice structure beyond what can be solely accounted for by the dimensions of the individual atoms and bond angles. Further investigation into these factors could

provide deeper insights into the structural properties and behaviour of Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) metal soaps.

It seems that the molecular axes of the soap molecules are inclined to the basal planes to some extent. The metal ions cobalt and praseodymium fit into spaces between the oxygen atoms of the ionized carboxyl group without causing significant strain on the bond. In the diffraction pattern of cobalt and praseodymium (Caprate), numerous diffraction peaks are observed in the intermediate range. These peaks arise from X-ray diffraction by atomic planes with much smaller separations than the basal planes. The calculated spacing from these peaks corresponds to the lateral distances between soap molecules in a layer.

Based on the theory and data, it is suggested that the metal ions in Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) soaps are arranged in equally spaced parallel planes within the soap crystal. The structure consists of a zigzag chain of fully extended fatty acid radicals. Double-layer structures, with molecule axes somewhat inclined to the basal planes, can be observed on both sides of each basal plane in both cobalt and praseodymium soaps. This theory was originally proposed by *Vold and Hattiangdi* (Vold, & Hattiangdi, 1949). This proposed arrangement provides valuable insights into the spatial organization of molecules within the crystal lattice of Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) metal soaps, contributing to our understanding of their structural properties and potential applications.

The thermogravimetric analysis results are shown in Tables 6 and 7, (Figure 7,8). These tables show that the theoretically estimated weight of Cobalt and Praseodymium (Caprate) oxide is the same as that of the metal oxide's final residue. These oxides were created using the chemical formula of soaps.

Table 6. Thermogravimetric Data of Cobalt Caprate

S.No	Time (t-min.)	Temperature T(K)	Weight loss of Soap $W_x \times 10^6$ (g)	$dw/dt \times 10^2$	$W_r \times 10^6$
1	3	333	14	0.47	4456
2	5	373	67	1.33	4404
3	6	393	88	1.46	4383
4	10	473	148	1.48	4322
5	13	533	269	2.07	4202
6	15	573	451	3.01	4019
7	16	593	570	3.56	3901
8	17	613	852	5.01	3618
9	18	633	1450	8.05	3021
10	19	653	2328	12.25	2143
11	20	673	3049	15.25	1421
12	23	733	4167	18.12	303
13	28	833	4433	15.83	38
14	33	933	4425	13.41	45
15	38	1033	4468	11.76	2
16	40	1073	4471	11.18	0
17	42	1113	4471	10.64	0

Figure 7. Thermogravimetric Analysis of Cobalt Caprate

Table 7. Thermogravimetric Data of Praseodymium Caprate

S.No	Time (t-min.)	Temperature T(K)	Weight loss of Soap $W_x 10^6(g)$	$dw/dt \times 10^2$	$W_r \times 10^6$
1	3	333	44	1.48	4338
2	5	373	147	2.95	4234
3	6	393	218	3.64	4163
4	10	473	470	4.7	3911
5	13	533	565	4.35	3816
6	15	573	592	3.94	3790
7	16	593	611	3.82	3770
8	17	613	649	3.82	3733
9	18	633	710	3.95	3672
10	19	653	794	4.18	3588
11	20	673	922	4.61	3459
12	23	733	2496	10.85	1886
13	28	833	4068	14.53	314
14	33	933	4162	12.61	220
15	38	1033	4359	11.47	22
16	40	1073	4382	10.95	0
17	42	1113	4382	10.43	0

Figure 8. Thermogravimetric Analysis of Praseodymium Caprate

The thermal decomposition of cobalt and praseodymium (Caprate) has been elucidated using the Freeman-Carroll (1958) and Coats-Redfern (1964) equations.

Freeman and Carroll developed a rate expression to describe thermal decomposition. This expression can be represented as:

$$\frac{\Delta \log\left[\frac{d\omega}{dt}\right]}{\Delta[\log(\omega_r)]} = -\frac{E}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{\Delta\left[\frac{1}{T}\right]}{\Delta[\log(\omega_r)]} + n \quad (1)$$

The variables represent the absolute scale of temperature (T), gas constant (R), activation energy (E), order of decomposition reaction (n), and density of state (dω/dt). Coats and Redfern proposed the following rate equation:

$$\log\left(\frac{\alpha}{T^2}\right) = \log\left(\frac{AR}{aE}\right) \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E}\right] - \frac{E}{2.303RT} \quad (2)$$

The variables α, T, R, A, a, E, and n represent the absolute temperature, gas constant, heating rate, activation energy, reaction order, proportion of soap decomposed, and frequency factor, respectively. According to the findings, soaps containing cobalt and praseodymium, particularly those derived from caprate, have started to decompose. The activation energy must be between 0.030 kJ/mol¹ for this reaction.

Conclusion

In metallic soaps, a comprehensive approach is used to investigate the solid-state physicochemical properties of cobalt and praseodymium soaps (Caprate). In the conclusion of the studies, researchers analyze the crystalline characteristics, molecular structure, and temperature responses of these compounds using methods such as thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), infrared (IR) spectroscopy, and others. Infrared spectroscopy is an effective approach for analysing soap molecule structure because it lets us see functional groups and chemical interactions in exquisite detail. Meanwhile, thermal gradient chromatography (TGA) provides information on these compounds' stability and breakdown patterns under various temperature conditions. Finally, an XRD analysis demonstrates that the soaps are crystalline, offering light on certain structural arrangements and crystallographic phases. These analytical approaches illuminate the solid-state physicochemical properties of cobalt and praseodymium caprate soaps, including their molecular composition, thermal behavior, and crystallographic characteristics.

Author Contributions

Suchi Singh: Investigation, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Data curation.

Kavita Poonia: Writing - review & editing, Supervision.

R.K. Shukla: Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Supervision.

Conflicts of Interest

The Authors state no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The raw data can be obtained on request from the corresponding author.

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